

CHROMATOGRAPHIC ESTIMATION OF ALLOYS. PART I. COPPER IN BRASS AND BRONZE

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Conditions for obtaining uniform and sharp chromatograms of copper ion has been studied with reference to the adsorbent, size of tube, strength of solution and developer. Using potassium ferrocyanide as developer, a method of estimating copper by the use of adsorption isotherm has been evolved. The method has been used to estimate copper in brass and bronze to an accuracy of 99%.

Lange and Nadel (*Z. Elektrochem*, 1936, **42**, 210) and Schwab and co-workers (*Naturwiss.*, 1937, **28**, 44; *Z. angew. Chem*, 1937, **50**, 546, 691; 1938, **51**, 709) have made considerable contribution to the study of inorganic chromatography and laid down conditions under which chromatograms could be obtained. However, less attention has been paid till now to inorganic than to organic aspect of the subject on the quantitative side. Cook (Lecture on chromatographic analysis, Institute of Chemistry of Great Britain and Ireland, 1941, p. 29) draws attention to the promising field of chromatographic estimation of one ion from the dimensions of the chromatic zone and the value of this method in the analysis of steel and other alloys. Since this method is elegant and should prove useful in the rapid analysis of a large number of alloys in any technical laboratory, investigations on the quantitative analysis of brass and bronze were undertaken by this. It could be seen from the experimental details, mentioned below, that great care has to be taken to get absolutely sharp bands and uniform zones.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the Adsorbent—Alumina used in this investigation was prepared as follows: Pure potash alum (500 g.) was dissolved in water to make a saturated solution and strong ammonia added in small quantities, while the solution was kept stirred and warm. The precipitated alumina was taken up with a large quantity of distilled water, decanted and filtered. The precipitate was washed several times with distilled water to remove the last traces of sulphates and ammonia, and dried at 120°. The dry alumina was powdered and sieved at 100 to 120 mesh; this sample was used as the adsorbent.

Arrangement of the Column.—The apparatus used was the simple one, similar to the one described by Teswett (*Ber. Deut. bot. Ges.*, 1906, **24**, 384) with or without suction. Schwab and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) filled the tube with a thick suspension of alumina and heated it to 70° to 80° to make it air-free and to obtain a workable packing by alternate sharp suction and tapping. Trials likewise here proved not satisfactory to get sharp and well defined separation. The end of the chromatogram was not sharp but showed a saw-edged appearance. Further, on allowing the column to drain itself after washing with water it was found that small air bubbles still remained which, while working, slowly moved with the liquid passing through and produced diffuse extension of the chromatogram at the walls of the tube.

It has also been mentioned by the above workers that alumina shows good adsorption if moistened with a liquid of p_H value of 9.4. In view of these the following procedure was adopted and was found to give sharp bands without any diffusion.

Tubes (25 cm. long and proper width, as described and decided by the following

experiments) were filled with the prepared alumina made into a paste with water p_H of which was adjusted to 9.4 by the addition of a small quantity of ammonia. The p_H was noted by the addition of B.D.H. Universal indicator so that a portion of the water gave greenish blue colour with green predominating. The tubes so filled were immersed in a tall jar of water of the same p_H and kept overnight. It was found by this procedure that all the air-bubbles were slowly removed and there was complete elimination of non-uniform packing. The results were remarkably good in that there was absolutely no diffusion or saw-edged end of the band. The tubes at the lower ends at the constriction contained a small piece of asbestos wool plug.

The Choice of the Diameter and the Quantity of Solution to be Tested.—The prepared column was set up over a filter flask and a gentle suction applied. It was washed several times with water taking care that the top of the column there was always in water or solution and no air was sucked through the column. Measured amounts of $M/200$ solution of copper nitrate were added gently by pouring it at the top. Gentle suction was applied; it was washed five times with water. The chromatogram was developed by 2 c. c. of ammonium sulphide solution saturated with H_2S . A few preliminary trials showed that copper nitrate 1 to 5 c. c. solution of strength $M/200$ and tubes of 0.7 cm. diameter gave suitable lengths of bands, which were sharp and uniform. The results could be reproduced.

The Choice of the Developer.—A solution of ammonium sulphide, saturated with hydrogen sulphide, was usually used by Schwab and others for chromatographing copper. The band is black in colour. For zinc the colour is yellow with the adsorption of ammonium sulphide. Experiments were also tried with potassium ferrocyanide as the developer; copper gives the usual brown-red colour and zinc has no colour. The following table gives the observations on the development of the chromatogram of copper with these developers at different concentrations of the solutions of copper.

TABLE I

Adsorbent: alumina, pure B.D.H. from stock.

Quantity of the solution = 1 c.c. of copper nitrate.

Conc. of the soln.	Length of band.	Remarks.
(NH ₄) ₂ S saturated with H ₂ S as developer.		
$M/25$	7.0 cm.	Uniform with a little diffusion at the end
$M/50$	3.7	Uniform and better than previous one
$M/100$	1.8	Good and sharp band
$M/200$	0.9	Good and very sharp band
Potassium ferrocyanide as developer.		
$M/25$	7.0 cm.	Good but not uniform
$M/50$	3.6	The band better than with ammonium sulphide
$M/100$	1.7	Sharp band, good and no diffusion
$M/200$	0.85	Beautiful brown band with a sharp line of demarcation between the white and the brown zones

At lower concentration of the solution the adsorption was good.

Next experiments were conducted by converting the copper solution into its complex with ammonia. The following table gives the data.

TABLE II

The conditions are the same as in Table I.
Cuprammonium complex.

Conc.	Length of band.	Remarks
M/50	8.0 cm.	
M/100	6.1	Pale blue band, uniform and very sharp. No diffusion in all cases.
M/200	4.6	
M/400	3.4	
M/800	2.4	

Having now obtained the conditions for obtaining the best chromatogram for the copper ion, the quantitative estimation of copper in the alloys was undertaken. The adsorbent used in the estimation was the one prepared as described in the beginning of this paper.

Estimation of Copper from the Dimensions of the Chromatograms.—Martin and Synge (*Biochem. J.*, 1941, 35, 1358) in their studies on partition chromatography have compared the adsorption column to the fractional distillation column and have derived expressions for known concentrations of the substance adsorbed at every stage of the chromatogram. But in these cases of inorganic salts, the adsorption of the metallic ion is strong and irreversible. The chromatograms could be made to be uniform throughout by carefully adjusting the conditions and working with dilute solutions. In dilute solution as the liquid descends, the cations are completely adsorbed at each layer and the band is uniform. Thus the process is not one of equilibrium at each stage. There is also absence of information in the case of adsorption chromatograms about the effect of concentration on the adsorption coefficient, even if there be equilibrium. Hence, the safest guide available in all adsorption processes is the Freundlich's equation and it could be used to find a relation between the length of the adsorbed column and the quantity of the metal ion (here copper).

Thus,

$$x/m = a C^{1/n}$$

where the symbols have the usual significance.

Under uniform adsorption from dilute solutions,

$$x/m = x/\pi r^2 \cdot h \cdot d$$

where r is the radius of the tube and h is the height of the chromatogram and d , the density of the adsorbent.

For different concentrations C_1 and C_2 ,

$$(C_1/C_2)^{1/n} = h_2/h_1$$

where h_1 and h_2 correspond to the length of the chromatogram at C_1 and C_2 respectively. For different values of C and h one can obtain values of n for each ion measured chromatographically with suitable dimensioned tubes.

Thus, for copper with the alumina, prepared as mentioned above, with a tube of diameter of 0.7 cm. we get using 2 c. c. of the solution and developing with potassium ferrocyanide the following height of chromatograms.

TABLE III

Conc.	Height of chromatogram.	$1/n$.
(a) M/25	4.50 cm.	-1.23 between (d) and (a)
(b) M/50	1.95	-1.23 ,, (b) and (c)
(c) M/100	0.85	-1.23 ,, (b) and (a)
(d) M/200	0.35	-1.24 , (c) and (d)

The constancy of the factor $1/n$ between different concentrations of copper nitrate solutions shows that the above equation could be applied to estimate metallic ions in solution.

The equation applied to data presented in Table II with cuprammonium complex gives a constant of -0.38.

The above quantitative method developed has been applied to the estimation of copper in brass and bronze and the results compared with that obtained by iodimetric estimation of copper in the same samples.

Estimation of Copper in Brass and Bronze.—Weighed quantities of less than a gram of the alloys were dissolved in concentrated nitric acid and the solution was made up to 200 c. c. The above solution (2 c. c.) was allowed to pass through the adsorbent. The column was washed with distilled water five times. The alumina used in these experiments was the one prepared from alum as described previously.

The developer used was potassium ferrocyanide. The ammonium sulphide developer was not used since there was a tendency for slight diffusion at the Cu—Zn interface. A number of chromatograms was prepared. The length of the column in each was the same. The alloys used were standard ones supplied by Flatters and Garnett, Manchester, with certificate of analysis. The results are tabulated below.

TABLE IV

*Copper in brass and bronze.*Factor $1/n = -1.23$.

Wt. of material.	Height of column.	Cu analysed iodimetrically.	Cu values given by Suppliers.	Cu estimated chromatographically.
Brass 1				
0.6580 g	5.50 cm	90.25%	90.00%	90.67%
0.9670	4.20	50.01	50.00	49.56
Bronze 2				
0.7162	4.50	70.15	70.00	70.70

The accuracy of 99%, as obtained above by this method, is fairly good for rapid analysis of a number of samples. For different cations the value of $1/n$ under conditions of experiment has to be found out and used.